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Measuring Effluent Flow in a Biogas Digester: A Practical and Affordable Tipping Bucket Design

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Abstract

Measuring effluent flow in biogas digesters is crucial for improving their performance and gaining deeper insights into their operation. This thesis focuses on the design, development, and testing of a cost-effective and practical tipping bucket system for measuring effluent flow rates in biogas digesters. Biogas digesters play a vital role in reducing methane emissions by converting organic waste, manure, and feces into biogas and a nutrient-rich fertilizer.

This research addresses three primary questions: how to select durable and affordable materials, how to optimize the design for ease of manufacturing and assembly, and how to achieve a flow measurement accuracy of 10%. Acrylic was identified as the most suitable material because it is durable, compatible with fluids, and works well with the chosen manufacturing method: laser cutting. Through an iterative prototyping process, the final design was developed: a lightweight and compact tipping bucket system. This design was tested at flow rates ranging from 6 to 9 liters per minute, and calibration efforts resulted in a strong correlation between tipping frequency and actual flow, achieving an R^2 value of 0.9213.

Although the system produced promising results, further improvements are needed. Inconsistent water flow during testing affected the calibration accuracy, and the system would benefit from using a higher-resolution Hall sensor for more precise measurements. Future research should focus on improving the experimental setup, validating the calibration formula, and assessing the system's long-term durability under real-world biogas digester conditions.

This research demonstrates the potential of a simple and affordable tipping bucket system to accurately measure effluent flow in biogas digesters. With further development, it could become a valuable tool for optimizing biogas systems and supporting efforts to make them more efficient and sustainable.

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

Climate change is one of the most pressing challenges of our time, demanding urgent solutions to protect the environment and public health. One of the most critical steps is the shift to renewable fuels for energy, heating, and transportation. This is especially important in rural areas, where sustainable energy sources are not yet easily accessible. For countries aiming to reach net-zero emissions by 2050, using and supporting renewable fuels has become essential (Farghali et al., 2022). Additionally, promoting the use of sustainable energy in low- and middle-income countries has been highly encouraged by the nations involved in the Paris Agreement, as it provides the opportunity to purchase carbon certificates (United Nations, 2015). Supporting sustainable energy projects can help these countries achieve their net-zero targets (Daharwal et al., 2023).

A key part of tackling climate change is understanding the sources of greenhouse gas emissions. Greenhouse gases are made up of 79.9% carbon dioxide, 11.1% methane, 6.1% nitrous oxide, and 3.1% fluorinated gases. While carbon dioxide is the most significant component, methane is approximately 28 times more effective at trapping heat in the atmosphere, making its impact crucial in the fight against climate change. Additionally, over the past 20 years, methane concentration in the atmosphere has more than doubled (US EPA, 2025a). As a result, methane has become a significant concern and plays a crucial role in global warming efforts. But this raises an important question: Where does methane come from, and how can we reduce its emissions?

Figure 1: Total greenhouse gas emissions (US EPA, 2025b)

Figure 2: Sources of methane emissions (US EPA, 2025a)

One of the largest sources of methane is organic waste in landfills. According to the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency organic waste accounts for 24% of landfill waste but is responsible for 58% of the methane produced in landfills (Krause et al., 2023). Landfills are the third-largest global source of methane emissions, contributing 11% of total emissions (Global Methane Initiative, 2011). However, landfills are not the only source. The livestock industry also

contributes around 34% of global methane emissions. Of these emissions, 9% come solely from the manure management (US EPA, 2025b), since methane is produced when manure is stored in oxygen-deprived conditions (Hidayat et al., 2021).

Additionally, human feces are estimated to contribute 7-10% of global methane emissions. However, this figure is likely an underestimation, as it primarily accounts for emissions from wastewater in sewerage sanitation systems, leaving out methane generated from non-sewered sources, such as open defecation and pit latrines (Agarwal et al., 2023). These unregulated waste management systems often create conditions that promote methane production, intensifying the issue (Cheng et al., 2022).

Beyond their impact to greenhouse gas emissions, the improper disposal of human feces has serious public health consequences. Poor sanitation and unsafe drinking water are leading causes of diarrheal diseases, which are the third leading cause of death among children worldwide (WHO, 2024). That's why finding alternative methods for storing organic waste, manure and human waste, as well as capturing its methane emissions, is a crucial step in minimizing overall methane emissions.

1.2 Biogas Digesters

Biogas digesters present a promising solution to these environmental and waste management challenges by converting organic waste and feces into valuable biogas and fertilizer. These systems operate through a biological process in which bacteria break down the feedstock—typically a mixture of organic waste and feces—under controlled anaerobic conditions. The primary output of this process is biogas, which usually consists of 50-75% methane, 25-50% carbon dioxide, and 2-8% other gases, such as hydrogen sulfide and ammonia. The biogas can be captured and utilized for various purposes, including generating electricity, providing heat, or fueling burners for cooking. In addition to biogas, another valuable by-product is the thick, nutrient-rich sludge known as effluent or slurry, which can be used as a potent fertilizer for agricultural purposes, enriching the soil with essential nutrients and reducing the need for chemical fertilizers (Da Costa Gomez, 2013).

Biogas digesters have been used for over 70 years, but they are still not widely adopted. This is mainly because they are expensive to install, and there hasn't been much technological improvement over the years (Amuzu-Sefordzi et al., 2018). Despite their potential to provide renewable energy and manage waste, biogas systems need improved efficiency and accessibility to reach larger-scale implementation. However, some countries are beginning to recognize the potential of biogas. For example, Switzerland has announced plans to build over 10,000 biogas digesters in Malawi. Switzerland then can benefit from claiming certificates for the resulting emission reduction, helping them achieve their net-zero goals in 2050 (KliK International, 2023).

To make biogas digesters work better and encourage more people to use them, their performance needs to be improved. One important step is to measure the flow rates of the feedstock going into the digester and the effluent coming out of it. These flow rates are crucial for keeping the digester running efficiently. If the flow isn't managed properly, it can lead to problems like overloading or incomplete digestion, which reduce the amount of biogas produced. A low-cost, easy-to-manufacture solution for measuring these flow rates is essential to advance the practical use and performance of biogas digesters.

Figure 3: In-ground bag biogas digester (Rich, 2010)

Figure 4: Biogas digester (Barth, 2018)

1.3 Justification and Research Questions

This thesis addresses a key gap in biogas technology by designing and testing a tipping bucket system capable of accurately measuring the effluent flow rate. The system needs to be cost-effective, easy to manufacture, and reliable in both operation and measurement. The goal is to use the data collected by the system to improve the performance of biogas digesters, making them more efficient and sustainable. To achieve this, the thesis addresses three main research questions:

- What materials can be used for constructing the tipping bucket to achieve a balance between cost efficiency and durability in a biogas digester environment?
- What is the optimal design of the tipping bucket that ensures ease of manufacturing and assembly?
- What specific dimensions and configurations of the tipping bucket can achieve a flow measurement accuracy of $\pm 10\%$ for biogas digesters?

2 Methods

2.1 Material Selection

The first research question of this thesis aimed to identify a suitable material that can withstand external effects, the effluent inside the tipping bucket, while also being cost-effective. One of the key constraints was that the material had to be compatible with laser cutting, which significantly narrowed down the options. The laser cutter, Trotec Q400, can cut materials such as wood, acrylic, and plastic. Since wood is not suitable for use with water or other liquids, the choice was limited to plastic and acrylic. A brief comparison was conducted using Granta EduPack to determine which material would be the most appropriate. Durability in water and the Young's modulus were compared, with elongation limited to 20% strain to ensure that the material would not be too flexible, given that the tipping bucket may consist of larger pieces. As a result, three materials were found to be suitable, as shown in Figure 5: Polyoxymethylene (POM), acrylic, and Acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS). However, POM, being the most expensive at nearly 330 CHF/m², was ruled out for this project (Kunststoff-Shop.ch, 2025). Ultimately, the decision was made to use acrylic, as it is easily available and offers various options, such as transparent glass and translucent colored plates.

Figure 5: Granta Edu Pack analysis, comparing suitability with water to the Young's modulus of the material

2.2 Experimental Setup and Data Collection

The experimental setup used for data collection is shown in figure.

Figure 6: Experimental setup with the water flow in blue and the electrical circuit for the hall sensors

Two Hall sensors were included in the setup. One was placed at the water tap to measure water flow, with a measurable range between 1 L/min and 30 L/min. The second sensor was attached to the cube of the tipping bucket with a measuring range of 1 tip per second. A magnet on the moving part of the bucket allowed the sensor to detect each tip. Data was recorded using an Arduino board, with measurements taken every second. The configuration of the electrical circuit is also illustrated in Figure 6. The data was stored in CSV format with the structure: YYYY/MM/DD HH:MM:SS, FLOW [L/min], TIP [0 or 1]. The tapwater was directed into the tipping bucket via a hose connected to the top of the cube. The water that exited at the outlet of the cube was collected in buckets, which were replaced when full.

To ensure that the testing setup achieved an accuracy of at least 10%, the Hoeffding inequality was used to calculate how often the bucket must tip (Duchi, 2025)

$$P(|\hat{\mu} - \mu| \geq \epsilon) \leq 2e^{-2N\epsilon^2} \quad (2.1)$$

Where ϵ is the accuracy, $\hat{\mu}$ the empirical mean, μ the true mean, P the probability and N the minimum number of measurements to estimate the true mean within a specified error margin. To calculate the needed number of samples N for a given accuracy, ϵ the Hoeffding inequality can be rearranged and simplified as following

$$N \geq \frac{-\ln\left(\frac{P}{2}\right)}{2\epsilon^2}$$
(2.2)

For an accuracy level of $\epsilon = 0.1$, the minimum number of measurements becomes

$$N \geq \frac{1}{\epsilon^2} = \frac{1}{0.1^2} = 100$$
(2.3)

This calculation determined that the tipping bucket needed to tip at least 100 times during the experiment. Considering the flow sensor's limit of one tip per second, a tipping interval of three seconds was selected, with a measurement time of five minutes at the highest flow rate of 9 L/min. Based on the maximum flow rate and the three-second tipping interval, the bucket's minimum tipping volume was calculated as following:

$$V = \frac{Q}{n_{tips}} = \frac{9}{20} = 0.45,$$
(2.4)

where V is the required minimum tipping volume in L, Q the flow in L/min, and n_{tips} is the number of bucket tips per minute.

2.3 First Prototype

2.3.1 Design

The first prototype was created to explore the overall design and functionality of the tipping bucket system. It was inspired by similar designs used for rain gauge systems, as seen in (Wilson et al., 2014).

Figure 7: Tipping bucket rain gauge (Wilson et al., 2014)

This initial version was primarily intended to test the feasibility of laser cutting as a manufacturing method and to evaluate the mechanics of the tipping bucket. The focus was on the bucket mechanism and the funnel at the bottom, which directed the effluent to an outlet.

The prototype was constructed using MDF since it's more affordable than acrylic. The sheets were joined using finger joints to enhance stability when glued. To allow water to flow out after passing through the tipping bucket, a four-part funnel was designed with a 10% slope. This funnel was connected to a hose attachment for the outlet.

The tipping bucket was mounted inside a cube supported by four stilts, allowing the water to flow freely beneath the structure. The bucket was secured with two M4 screws and lock nuts to ensure stability. White silicone sealant was applied to all gaps to make the construction watertight.

Figure 8: Measurements of the first prototype

Figure 9: Four-part funnel of the first prototype

2.3.2 Results and Improvements for the Second Prototype

The first prototype was primarily tested for mechanical functionality rather than quantitative performance, as it was built with a different material. Testing was conducted with a flow rate of approximately 4.5 L/min. Several areas for improvement were identified:

- 1. Increase space between the funnel and the tipping bucket:** The space between the tipping bucket when it's at full tilt and resting on the funnel was too small. This stopped the water from flowing to the outlet properly. The tipping bucket should be mounted higher, and screws could be added on the sides of the cube to prevent excessive tilting. This would create more space for the water.

2. **Tilted sheets in tipping bucket:** The tilted sheets could align with the edge of the tipping bucket to improve structural stability.
3. **Create a protective cube enclosure:** The entire setup should be enclosed in one large protective cube with only holes for the inlet and outlet. This would improve the appearance while also protecting against external interruptions or damage.
4. **See-through window:** Adding a transparent front window would allow for easy observation of internal components and the flow process during operation.
5. **Removable top for maintenance:** The top of the cube should be designed to be easily removable, enabling quick access for maintenance and repairs if needed.

Figure 10: The small gap between the funnel and the tipping bucket

Figure 11: Tilted sheets that are not aligned with the edge marked in red

2.4 Second Prototype

2.4.1 Design

All the insights from the first prototype were incorporated into the second prototype, which focused on the required size to measure the maximum flow of 9 L/min and the performance of the bucket using acrylic sheets. In the first prototype, an acrylic tipping bucket was tested to determine the flow rate at which it tipped every three seconds. Based on this, the size for the second prototype was scaled up to achieve the desired flow rate of 9 L/min. However, due to the Hall sensor's inability to measure flows below 1 L/min, the acrylic bucket tipped every 3.48 seconds during tests with a flow of 1.188 L/min (F_m) instead of every three seconds. Using this data, the tipping volume was scaled for a flow of 9 L/min (F_w):

$$\text{Cubic scaling factor} = \frac{F_w}{F_m} = \frac{9}{1.188} = 7.576 \quad (2.5)$$

$$\text{Linear scaling factor} = \sqrt[3]{x} = \sqrt[3]{7.576} = \mathbf{1.964} \quad (2.6)$$

where F_m is the measured flow in L/min, F_w the wanted flow in L/min and V the needed tipping volume for F_w in L.

The second prototype was therefore constructed using a linear scaling factor of 2, effectively doubling the volume of the first prototype. Acrylic sheets were chosen for construction to match the final product. Unlike the first prototype, the cube was not standing on stilts, so the outlet hole couldn't be on the bottom. This required the funnel to be reconfigured into a three-part system and the outlet to be on the side. The tipping bucket was mounted at a maximum tilting angle of 30 degrees and positioned further from the funnel to increase the space between the funnel and the tipping bucket. The acrylic sheets were glued together and sealed with clear silicone, just like the first prototype. The tipping bucket was secured with a M6 galvanized threaded rod and locknuts.

Figure 12: Measurements of the second prototype

Figure 13: Three-part funnel of the second prototype

2.4.2 Results and Improvements for the Final Design

The second prototype was tested using the same setup as the first but with the target maximum flow rate of 9 L/min. Data was collected via video recordings due to issues with both Hall sensors. The tests showed that the bucket tipped more often than intended (every 1.5 – 2 seconds) and held a smaller tipping volume (0.38 L instead of 0.45 L), even though the entire setup was very large. Therefore, the bucket's momentum needed to be adjusted to ensure the bucket tipped at the required 0.45 L every 3 seconds for the maximum flow of 9 L/min.

To solve these issues, the following solutions were considered:

1. **Weight on top of the tilted sheets.** This would change the tipping momentum.

Figure 14: Weight on top of tilted sheets

2. **Moving weight underneath the bucket.** The weight could move from side to side to adjust the momentum dynamically, and the weight could be lighter than for the first solution.

Figure 15: Moving weight underneath the bucket

3. **New axis position.** The tipping bucket would rotate around a different point, which changes the momentum.

Figure 16: New Axis position

Additionally, the outlet hole was too small, causing water to accumulate in the cube, as seen in Figure 17. Making the hole bigger would solve this issue. On top of that, the entire setup was very large, making the entire setup impractical and cost-inefficient, since this setup used almost 2 m² of acrylic sheets.

Figure 17: Accumulated water in cube

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Final Design

For the final design, every solution that was found to improve the momentum for the second prototype needed to be considered. Three momentum balance calculations (detailed in Appendix A) were made to determine the best solution. The results for the first two solutions showed:

1. **Weight on top of the tilted sheets.** This would require a weight of 0.0295 kg.
2. **Moving weight underneath the bucket.** This would require a weight of 0.0111 kg.

While the extra weights provided a solution, they were not the most elegant, as they required additional material and were not the easiest to implement. Therefore, the third solution was chosen, as it offered a simpler approach without the need for extra materials.

Figure 18: Measurements of the final design

With that another momentum balance was calculated to determine the required height of the axis. To minimize the cube height, the tipping bucket was designed with a maximum tilting angle of 26 degrees, as shown in Figure 19. The dimensions of the tipping bucket were finalized as follows: height $H = 9.5$ cm, width $W = 18$ cm, length $L = 32$ cm. These dimensions allowed the bucket to hold 0.45 liters without being excessively large. Based on these specifications, the axis height was calculated to be 0.86 cm below the tipping bucket, shown in Figure 20. Since the

calculated axis height placed it below the tipping bucket, the designs of both the tipping bucket and the surrounding cube were modified accordingly, as shown in Figure 18 above.

Figure 19: New maximum tilting angle

Figure 20: New axis height

3.2 Assembly

The final assembly of the tipping bucket system required several materials, including 5 mm-thick white and transparent acrylic sheets. A galvanized M6 threaded rod, 20 cm long, secured the tipping bucket, along with two locknuts, standard nuts, and washers. To ensure stability and water tightness, Soudal Fix ALL Crystal glue and Sista Bath & Kitchen silicone, both transparent, were used for bonding and sealing.

To prepare the components, the acrylic sheets were cut to the required dimensions using a Trotrec Q400 laser cutter. The cutting parameters varied depending on the type of acrylic: the white acrylic was cut with 100% power and 1% speed, requiring two passes, while the transparent acrylic was cut with 80% power and 0.5% speed in a single pass.

The assembly process began with constructing the main cube structure, excluding the funnel. Each joint of the cube was carefully glued and sealed to create a sturdy and water-tight base. Once the cube was complete, the funnel was attached to its designated position using the same adhesive and sealing methods.

While the cube and funnel were drying, the tipping bucket was assembled separately. After ensuring that all components were properly sealed and dried, the tipping bucket was carefully positioned inside the cube. To secure it in the center, three washers were placed on either side between the tipping bucket and the walls of the cube. The assembly was then fastened using nuts and locknuts and tightened from both the inside and outside of the structure, as shown in Figure 21. Four box latches were attached to the top of the bucket to ensure that the removable lid stayed securely in place during operation, as shown in Figure 22.

Figure 21: Washers and nuts underneath tipping bucket

Figure 22: Final Design with box latches

3.3 Cost

The total cost for a single tipping bucket is 143.76 CHF, as shown in Table 1. Since the final design was constructed using materials purchased in Switzerland and without benefiting from quantity discounts, the cost per unit is relatively high. The primary factor contributing to the high cost are the acrylic sheets. These were sourced from a Swiss supplier, which not only sold the material but also cut the sheets to the required size to fit into the laser cutter—an additional service that significantly increased their price. Securing a more affordable source for the acrylic sheets or taking advantage of quantity discounts could reduce the overall cost of producing the tipping bucket.

Table 1: List of materials and costs for the final product

Material	Amount	Cost p.p [CHF]	Total Cost [CHF]
Acrylic sheet white, 60 cm x 75 cm	1	41.25	41.25
Acrylic sheet white, 60 cm x 50 cm	1	27.5	27.5
Acrylic sheet transparent, 75 cm x 50 cm	1	40.00	40.00
M6 galvanized threaded rod, 22 cm	1	0.20	0.20
Locknut	2	0.0565	0.11
Nut	2	0.0445	0.089
Washer	8	0.049	0.39
Box latch	4	6.50	26
Soudal Fix ALL Crystal glue (transparent)	0.5	6.65	3.25
Sista Bath & Kitchen silicone (transparent)	0.5	9.95	4.975
Total cost			143.76

3.4 Data Collection Process

After finalizing the design of the tipping bucket system, the next step was to test the setup and collect the necessary data. Since the system was designed to measure the effluent flow rate of a biogas digester, data collection was required to calibrate the tipping bucket accurately.

Data collection experiments were conducted for flow rates ranging from 6 to 9 L/min. As described in the experimental setup (Section 2.2), at least 100 tips were recorded for each flow rate to achieve an accuracy of 10%. Each flow rate was tested three times to ensure consistency and reliability. Table 2 shows the required timeframes for recording at least 100 tips for each flow rate.

Table 2: Measurable timeframe for each flow

Flow [L/min]	Volume to tip	Tips/min	Tips every x second	Timeframe for [min]
9	0.45	20.00	3.00	5.00
8	0.45	17.78	3.38	5.63
7	0.45	15.56	3.86	6.43
6	0.45	13.33	4.50	7.5

3.5 Calibration of the Final Design

For the calibration of the tipping bucket, measurements with the timeframes described in Table 2 were carried out. A key challenge during the process was the inconsistency of the lab setup. The tap supplying water for the testing setup, where the first hall sensor was installed, did not maintain a steady flow rate. Even after letting the water run for several minutes, the flow would either gradually increase or decrease over time. These fluctuations are illustrated in Figure 23 and Figure 24 below, showing flowrates 6 L/min and 9 L/min.

Figure 23: Decreasing flow over measurement time of 6 L/min

Figure 24: Increasing flow over measurement time for 9 L/min

To account for these variations during calibration, the average flow rate over the measurement period was calculated, along with the average number of tips per minute. The results of this analysis are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Measured data for all flows

Flow [L/min]	Tests #	Measured timeframe [min]	Average flow in timeframe [L/min]	Average tips per min
9	#1	5.00	9.155	19.8
	#2	5.00	9.057	19.2
	#3	5.00	9.074	19.2
8	#1	5.63	8.024	17.6
	#2	5.63	8.065	17.6
	#3	5.63	8.016	17.6
7	#1	6.43	7.150	16.02
	#2	6.43	7.079	13.38
	#3	6.43	6.977	13.07
6	#1	7.5	6.027	11.87
	#2	7.5	5.974	11.87
	#3	7.5	5.943	13.2

Using the derived and calculated data, the relationship between tips per minute and the average flow rate was plotted on a chart. From this chart, a linear optimization was calculated. Using this optimization, a formula can be derived that can be used to calibrate the tipping bucket and ensure accurate flow rate measurements.

Figure 25: Calibration diagram; Measured curve (blue curve), calibration curve (dotted curve)

The linear optimization for the calibration formula is as follows:

$$n_{tips} = 2.3993 \cdot \dot{V} - 2.2351 \quad (3.1)$$

Inversed relationship for the volumetric flow \dot{V} as a function of number of tips n_{tips} is:

$$\dot{V} = 20.4169 \cdot n_{tips} + 0.9316 \quad (3.2)$$

This equation allows the tipping bucket to be calibrated, and the number of tips can provide information on the actual flow rate. Table 4 shows the number of tips and the corresponding flow in L/min, calculated using the calibration formula.

Table 4: Tips per minute with the corresponding calculated flow in L/min

Flow [L/min]	Volume to tip	Flow [L/min]	Volume to tip
1	1.3485	11	5.5175
2	1.7654	12	5.9344
3	2.1823	13	6.3513
4	2.5992	14	6.7682
5	3.0161	15	7.1851
6	3.433	16	7.602
7	3.8499	17	8.0189
8	4.2668	18	8.4358
9	4.6837	19	8.8527
10	5.1006	20	9.2696

The calibration curve, described by the equation, shows a good correlation between the number of tips and the flow rate. The R^2 value of 0.9213 indicates that most of the measurement points align well with the curve. However, there are some noticeable deviations in the diagram. For example, at a flow rate of around 6 L/min and 7 L/min, the measured points show a larger spread, which may result from the inconsistent flow rate at lower levels. Similarly, near 9 L/min, there is some slight variation in the alignment of the points with the curve. These deviations highlight the challenges of maintaining a steady flow during calibration.

4 Conclusions and Recommendations

This thesis aimed to develop a cost-effective and practical system to accurately measure the flow of the effluent of a biogas digester. The final tipping bucket system demonstrated that it can measure flow rates effectively by counting the number of tips. Its compact design and cost make it well-suited for use in rural and low-income settings.

One of the key aspects of this study was addressing the question of what materials can be used for constructing the tipping bucket to achieve a balance between cost efficiency and durability in the challenging biogas digester environment. Acrylic was identified as a suitable material, as it is both cost-effective and durable under the testing conditions. It proved to be resistant to moisture and suitable for use with water, making it appropriate for the biogas environment. However, further long-term testing in real biogas environments is recommended to confirm its durability over extended periods. For even greater durability, stainless steel could be considered for critical components, such as the rod, though this would increase the cost slightly.

The thesis also explored the optimal design of the tipping bucket to ensure ease of manufacturing and assembly. While the design was simple, some challenges were encountered during assembly. One significant issue was mounting the tipping bucket precisely in the center of the structure. The current mounting system, using a galvanized threaded rod and securing the bucket with nuts, made centering difficult and introduced friction that impacted the tipping motion. To improve the design, incorporating ball bearings into the mounting system could ensure smoother movement and simplify the assembly process.

Another issue identified was the bucket's sensitivity to minor tilts. When the system was not perfectly level, the water required to tip would vary between the sides of the tipping bucket, affecting the tipping accuracy. Addressing this would improve the system's overall performance.

The third research question focused on determining the specific dimensions and configurations of the tipping bucket that would achieve a flow measurement accuracy of 10% for biogas digesters. The calibration process showed promising results, with an R^2 value of 0.9213, indicating a strong correlation between the calibration curve and the actual curve. However, challenges during the calibration process impacted the accuracy of measurements.

One major issue was the inconsistent water flow from the testing setup, which likely affected the accuracy of the calibration. To address this challenge, future research should focus on improving the testing setup by using a regulated, consistent water supply. A steady flow rate would minimize fluctuations and help achieve more consistent results during calibration.

Another area that could be improved is the current Hall sensor at the tipping bucket, which only records data every second. Replacing the current sensor with a sensor capable of higher-

frequency measurements would help resolve errors when flow rates are close in speed and, for that, measure the same number of tips per minute.

Another important aspect this thesis did not address is validating the calibration formula. Validating the formula is crucial to ensuring that the measured flow rates accurately correspond to the actual flow. However, it is only practical to validate the calibration formula once the lab setup is more consistent and the Hall sensor is upgraded to a higher measurement frequency. Only with these improvements can the formula be properly validated.

Another issue is the leftover water or effluent in the tipping bucket when it doesn't reach the 0.45-liter tipping volume during the final tip, and the leftover liquid stays in the bucket. Over time, it can dry out, leaving residue that affects the bucket's movement and messes up the calibration for future use. This could lead to inaccurate measurements and possibly damage the system. To fix this, the bucket should be rinsed with clean water at the end of use to remove any remaining effluent. Also, the top cover of the bucket should be removed to let it dry completely, preventing any residue from interfering with the next use and ensuring consistent performance.

In conclusion, this thesis has developed a cost-effective and reliable tipping bucket system for measuring flow rates in biogas digesters, providing a strong foundation for real-world implementation, particularly in rural and low-income settings. While the system shows great potential, a few improvements—particularly in the calibration process—would enhance its accuracy. By addressing testing setup consistency and upgrading the sensor, the system could achieve even greater precision. Overall, this work offers a solid basis for the successful use of the system in biogas applications, with only minor refinements needed.

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Appendix A

This appendix contains the following calculations based on Figure 1:

- A.1 Calculation of the new axis height.
- A.2 Calculation of the extra weight on tilted sheets.
- A.3 Calculation of the moving weight underneath the bucket.

Figure 26: Illustrates the forces and corresponding moment arms used in all calculations

A.1 Calculation axis height

```
% Constants
alpha = 26; % Degree
beta = 71; % Degree
rho = 0.001156265119; % (kg/cm3) Density Acrylic: min. 0.00116918231,
max.0.0011627237185, Average: 0.001156265119
t = 0.5; % Thickness acrylic plates(cm)
mw = 0.45; % Tipping volume (kg)

% Values for B and H and L in cm (HB =H)
B = 18; % Width
H = 9.5; % Height
HB = 9.5; % Height

% variables
syms L tx

% Torque Height (tx)
% Lenght tipping bucket (L)

% Define coefficients(V,l1,l2,l3,l4,l5,l6)
V = H / sind(beta);
l1 = cosd(90-alpha) * (1/2 - tx) * H;
l2 = cosd(90-alpha) * (1-tx) * H - (cosd(beta-alpha) * (1/2) * V + cosd(90-
beta+alpha) * (1/2) * t);
l3 = cosd(90-alpha) * (1-tx) * H - cosd(180 - beta - alpha) * (1/2) * V +
cosd(alpha + beta - 90) * (1/2) * t;
l4 = cosd(90-alpha) * ((tx) * H + (1/2) * t);
l5 = cosd(beta) * V + (t/cosd(90-beta));
l6 = cosd(90-alpha) * HB;

% Mass plates and magnet in kg
G1 = L * HB * t * rho;
G2 = B * V * t * rho;
G3 = B * V * t * rho;
G4 = B * L * t * rho;
G6 = 0.002;

% Forces simplified without gravity
F1 = G1;
F2 = G2;
F3 = G3;
F4 = G4;
F5 = mw;
F6 = G6;

% Define equation
eq = 2 * F1 * l1 + F3 * l3 + F2 * l2 + F6 * l6 == F4 * l4 + F5 * l5;

% Set target Lenght
L_target = 32;
eq_with_L = subs(eq, L, L_target);
```

```
% Solve equation for tx
solution_tx = solve(eq_with_L, tx);

% convert into numerical values
solution_tx_num = double(solution_tx);
tx_in_cm = solution_tx_num * (H - 0.5)
tx_from_bottom_edge = tx_in_cm + 0.5

% Show solutions
disp('Possible tx so that L is 32 cm:');
disp(tx_in_cm);
disp('Measured from bottom edge:');
disp(tx_from_bottom_edge);
```

```
tx_in_cm =
```

```
-1.3623
```

```
tx_from_bottom_edge =
```

```
-0.8623
```

```
Possible tx so that L is 32 cm:
```

```
-1.3623
```

```
Measured from bottom edge:
```

```
-0.8623
```

```
Published with MATLAB® R2024b
```

A.2 Calculation extra weight on tilted sheets

```
% Constants
alpha = 30; % Degree
beta = 71; % Degree
rho = 0.001156265119; % (kg/cm3) Density Acrylic: min. 0.00116918231,
max.0.0011627237185, Average: 0.001156265119
t = 0.5; % Thickness acrylic plates(cm)
mw = 0.45; % Tipping volume (kg)

% Values for B and H and L in cm (HB =H)
B = 23; % Width
H = 15; % Height
HB = 15; % Height
L = 50; % Length

% variables Gx = extra weight
syms Gx

% Define coefficients(V,l1,l2,l3,l4,l5,l6,lx)
V = H / sind(beta);
l1 = cosd(90-alpha) * (1/2 - 1/6) * H;
l2 = cosd(90-alpha) * (5/6) * H - (cosd(beta-alpha) * (1/2) * V + cosd(90-
beta+alpha) * (1/2) * t);
l3 = cosd(90-alpha) * (5/6) * H - cosd(180 - beta - alpha) * (1/2) * V +
cosd(alpha + beta - 90) * (1/2) * t;
l4 = cosd(90-alpha) * ((1/6) * H + (1/2) * t);
l5 = cosd(beta) * V + (t/cosd(90-beta));
l6 = cosd(90-alpha) * HB
lx = l6

% Mass plates and magnet in kg
G1 = L * HB * t * rho;
G2 = B * V * t * rho;
G3 = B * V * t * rho;
G4 = B * L * t * rho;
G6 = 0.002 % kg

% Forces
F1 = G1;
F2 = G2;
F3 = G3;
F4 = G4;
F5 = mw;
F6 = G6;

% Define equation
eq = 2 * F1 * l1 + F3 * l3 + F2 * l2 + F6 * l6 + lx * Gx == F4 * l4 + F5 *
l5 ;
```

```
% Solve equation for Gx
solution = solve(eq, Gx);

solution_num = double(solution);

% Show solutions
disp('Gx in kg:');
disp(solution_num);
```

l6 =

7.5000

lx =

7.5000

G6 =

0.0020

Gx in kg:

0.0295

A.3 Calculation moving weight underneath bucket

```
% Constants
alpha = 30; % Degree
beta = 71; % Degree
rho = 0.001156265119; % (kg/cm3) Density Acrylic: min. 0.00116918231,
max.0.0011627237185, Average: 0.001156265119
t = 0.5; % Thickness acrylic plates(cm)
mw = 0.45; % Tipping volume (kg)

% Values for B and H and L in cm (HB =H)
B = 23; % Width
H = 15; % Height
HB = 15; % Height
L = 50; % Length

% variables Gx = extra weight
syms Gx

% Define coefficients(V,l1,l2,l3,l4,l5,l6,lx)
V = H / sind(beta);
l1 = cosd(90-alpha) * (1/2 - 1/6) * H;
l2 = cosd(90-alpha) * (5/6) * H - (cosd(beta-alpha) * (1/2) * V + cosd(90-
beta+alpha) * (1/2) * t);
l3 = cosd(90-alpha) * (5/6) * H - cosd(180 - beta - alpha) * (1/2) * V +
cosd(alpha + beta - 90) * (1/2) * t;
l4 = cosd(90-alpha) * ((1/6) * H + (1/2) * t);
l5 = cosd(beta) * V + (t/cosd(90-beta));
l6 = cosd(90-alpha) * HB
lx = 20

% Mass plates and magnet in kg
G1 = L * HB * t * rho;
G2 = B * V * t * rho;
G3 = B * V * t * rho;
G4 = B * L * t * rho;
G6 = 0.002 % kg

% Forces
F1 = G1;
F2 = G2;
F3 = G3;
F4 = G4;
F5 = mw;
F6 = G6;

% Define equation
eq = 2 * F1 * l1 + F3 * l3 + F2 * l2 + F6 * l6 + lx * Gx == F4 * l4 + F5 *
l5 ;
```

```
% Solve equation for Gx
solution = solve(eq, Gx);

solution_num = double(solution);

% Show solutions
disp('Gx in kg:');
disp(solution_num);
```

l6 =

7.5000

lx =

20

G6 =

0.0020

Gx in kg:

0.0111